

INSON-BU DUNYO FARZANDI

Shodiyev Jahongir Jo‘raqulovich

O‘zMU doktoranti

E-mail: shodiyevjahongir1985@gmail.com

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada Olam va borliq, dunyoning yaralishi va insonga taqdir etilgan hayot, tug‘ilish va o‘lim sirini bilishga qiziqish hamda inson tug‘ilgan daqiqadan boshlab ana shu koinot bilan bir butunlik, uyg‘unlik, bevositalik uzildi va ruh o‘sha paytda qay holatda bo‘lsa, shu holatda boshqa bir hayotini, jismoniy olamdagi hayotini yashay boshlashi bayon qilingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Olam va borliq, inson, qadr, qalb, jon, ruh, ruhiy quvvat, inson qalbi, ma’naviy-ruhiy olam.

ЧЕЛОВЕК – РЕБЕНОК ЭТОГО МИРА

Шодиев Джахангир Джуракулович

докторант УзМУ

E-mail: shodiyevjahongir1985@gmail.com

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье отсекаются Вселенная и существование, сотворение мира, а также интерес к познанию тайны жизни, рождения и смерти, а также с момента рождения единство, гармония, непосредственность с этой вселенной, и душа была в тот момент. Утверждается, что в этом состоянии он начнет проживать другую жизнь, свою жизнь в физическом мире.

Ключевые слова: Вселенная и существование, человек, ценность, сердце, душа, дух, духовная сила, человеческое сердце, духовно-духовный мир.

MAN IS A CHILD OF THIS WORLD.

Shodiyev Jahangir Jorakulovich

doctoral student of UzMU

E-mail: shodiyevjahongir1985@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In this article, the Universe and existence, the creation of the world, and the interest in knowing the secret of life, birth and death, and from the moment of birth, oneness, harmony, immediacy with this universe were cut off, and the soul was at that moment. It is stated that he will start living another life in this state, his life in the physical world.

Keywords: Universe and existence, human, value, heart, soul, spirit, spiritual power, human heart, spiritual-spiritual world.

It is natural for everyone to think about the universe and existence, the creation of the world and the secret of life, birth and death bestowed on man. However, due to the limited power of intelligence, it is difficult to reach the true and fundamental nature of this universe and being. In the last century, the doctrine and ideology of the Dahri system in our country tried to inculcate the belief that the universe and existence consist of material things, and that man was gradually created from an ape. Today, the nonsense and falsehood of this doctrine has been exposed, and it has become known that it is a fabrication. Because it is inconceivable that a creature, i.e., a self-created person, can create the world in which he lives. The divine books revealed to mankind - the Psalms, the Torah, the Injil and the Qur'an show that there is a Creator of this world and existence, that mankind is destined to live on earth, that this world is not eternal and that the people who came to this world on the Day of Judgment and Mahshar are good and bad. will be informed that he will give an account of his actions. The last of these divine books, the Holy Qur'an, freed from the misconceptions - polytheism, bid'ah and superstitions that have hardened in the human mind and imagination for many centuries, and gave a healthy and correct view about religion, the world and man. It calls for reflection: "So (O Muhammad!) Keep your face (yourself) in the right religion (Islam)!" There is no way to change the creation of God, who created people on that basis (your mind!) to the creation of God. This is the true religion, but many people do not know (it). When you submit yourselves to Him (hold on to the religion) and fear Him and perform the prayer perfectly, do not be of the polytheists" (Surah Rum, verses 30-31).

Modern numerology favors a simplified number and alphabetic code, without delving into the depths of kabbalistic cosmology ("kabbalah" - the doctrine that seeks the basis of all things in numbers and letters) and its esoteric (mysterious sciences) beliefs. This code is based on the theories of Pythagoras, a great mathematician and philosopher who spread the word in Ancient Greece.

At present, scientists of the world are looking at three different points of view about what is happening on Earth - whether the events are happening randomly or in

an orderly manner. These are, first, that there is unrest on Earth; secondly, both order and randomness reign on Earth at the same time; thirdly, the Earth is a complete order. Numerology rejects the first and second of the points of view shown above. According to numerologists, any random event or event does not happen by itself. All events obey the laws and have a completely regulated character. Further studies of scientists show that numerology is closely related to astrology. Experts in this field say that each planet corresponds to a certain number and affects a person's character - behavior or character.

A person is not an independent destiny, a transitory being consisting of a small body and a limited mind. He is a representative of society, humanity, and first of all, a citizen of the universe, the whole universe created by the Lord. Therefore, the veins of every human being are nourished by the veins of the entire universe, their psyche is shared with the Spirit of the Universe, their activity is in harmony with the movement of existence, and their destiny is scattered throughout the universe.

For example, if a small car passes by us, it affects our psyche. Now imagine that planets of different sizes, even incredibly huge, are floating above our heads. Some of them are tens of times larger than our Earth, which seems infinite to us. According to the law of gravitation, the whole universe is connected by invisible bonds - different forces. So, the movement of the planets and the Earth is subject to one law. Naturally, life on earth as a whole: nature, society, life, individual human destiny, psyche, even insects, whatever is in motion related to living, is subject to this general law of movement and living. Not only the fate of people depends on the movement of celestial bodies, but also the fate of our Earth. If it were not for this connection, our earth would have already left the solar system and wandered through the vast galaxy and collided with an object.

So, we live, so to speak, in an ocean of energies coming from the earth and coming from different planets.

However, we do not feel it, just like "the fish standing in the water did not feel the water" (Navoi's interpretation). Since ancient times, there have been two sciences dealing with such heavenly bodies. One of them is science, i.e. astronomy. In this science, the structure, location, and movement of celestial bodies are studied. The second is astrology. In it, the influence of heavenly bodies, their composition, and their movement on life on earth and the fate of people was studied.

In the past, many nations were well aware of astrology. In particular, 18 planets were known to the representatives of the ancient fire worship religion. In science, many of them were not known until now. Planets such as Uranus, Chiron, and Proserpina were not discovered long ago. Astrology is the basis of almost all ancient religions and mythology. In many pagan religions, the influence of the planets was highly deified

and they were considered gods. In ancient times, the seven planets that are closest to the earth and have an active influence were known. These are: the Sun, the Moon, Utorud, Venus, Mirrih, Mushtari and Zuhul, and expressions such as the deification of the number seven, the seven layers of the sky, and the seven climates are related to this.

If we mention the names of only a few of the most important people involved in this science, such as Farobi, Beruni, Qazizoda Rumi, Ulugbek, Ali Kushchi, many things come to life in our memory. In his work on astrology, Grandfather Farobi mentions that the correct rules of this science should be distinguished from fictions.

So, astrology is the oldest science formed on the basis of empirical knowledge. Because it is ancient, it is built on its own symbolic language. This makes it somewhat difficult for people to learn astrology directly. The main motto of astrologers is: "What is in the sky, is the same on earth."

From the moment a person is born, unity, harmony, immediacy with this universe is broken, and the soul, in whatever state it was at that time, began to live another life in this state, its life in the physical world. At this point, let's turn to an example, although it is not so appropriate: let's say that a foreigner came to your country, he learned your language, customs, way of life, and became a nation. It is possible, but many aspects of his psyche and inner world remain the same. He acquires new qualities in his new homeland, but his qualities in his homeland cease to develop in a certain sense. In the same way, a person's psyche is what it is at the time of birth.

Thus, every time the Sun crosses a 30-degree path, i.e., crosses one constellation and steps into another, its attitude, power, and influence on the Earth change. Meanwhile, the boundary between the constellations is extremely clear. As soon as the Sun moves into another sign, it begins to have a similar effect on the qualities of that sign. This, in turn, finds its expression in life on Earth, in the psyche, fate, and birth of people.

Therefore, among people, there are twelve archetypes - twelve zodiac signs - with different mentality, character, and characteristics. The names of the constellations are as follows: Hamal, Sawr, Javza, Cancer, Asad, Sunbula, Mezon, Aqrab, Kavs, Jadi, Jalv, Hut. Each planet is the "master" or "ruler" of a particular zodiac sign, it is "in the rut" in a particular zodiac sign, in its "honor sign" in a particular zodiac sign, and in a "fallen" position in a particular zodiac sign. So, each planet has four positions in the zodiac.

The characteristics of the constellations are gathered from the sum of the elements (Fire, Air, Earth, Water) to which they belong, and the qualities of the planets present in them in certain situations. In turn, these qualities are also manifested in the nature of people born in a certain zodiac sign.

Astrologers or astrologers believe that future events and events in society, and the fate of people can be predicted based on the position and movement of the stars and planets. For this reason, they made special horoscopes and expressed their views in them. Belief in astrologers is widespread in many countries. After the disintegration of the former Union, especially in the years of independence, interest in astrological views has revived. Today, various horoscopes are shown on radio and television and in the press.

After the theory of relativity was founded by Albert Einstein, representatives of other branches of science did not sit idly by, but philosophers first drew their own conclusions from it.

We believe that studying numbers and figures both horizontally and vertically, discovering their new aspects - content - essence, in other words, approaching them from a philosophical point of view, will lead humanity to new scientific horizons.

REFERENCES:

1. Azimov, A. A., & Avliyokulov, U. M. (2019). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ ЭПОХИ АБУ АБДУЛЛАХ РУДАКИ. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 560-562.
2. Темиров, Ш. Т., & Азимов, А. А. (2016). Экономический и культурный рост народов центральной азии в IX-X веках. In *Интеграция современных научных исследований в развитие общества* (pp. 104-105).
3. Азимов, А. А., & Темиров, Ш. Т. (2016). Политическая и социальная жизнь в бухарском эмирате во взглядах ахмада дониша. In *Интеграция современных научных исследований в развитие общества* (pp. 66-67).
4. Azimov, A. A. (2022). PHILOSOPHICAL AND ETHICAL IDEAS OF THE EARLY RENAISSANCE OF THE EAST IN CENTRAL ASIA AND THEIR REFLECTION IN THE VIEWS OF ZAKARIA AR RAZI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(7), 57-62.
5. Азимов, А. А., & Темиров, Ш. Т. (2016). КУЛЬТУРНАЯ И АРХИТЕКТУРНАЯ ВЗАИМОВЛИЯНИЯ ВОСТОКА И ВОСТОЧНОЙ ЕВРОПЫ С БУХАРОЙ. In *Современные тенденции развития науки и производства* (pp. 33-34).
6. Азимов, А. А. ўғли Рўзиёв, АШ (2022, December). ОСОБЕННОСТИ КНИГИ АВЕСТА. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS* (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 37-42).
7. ВЗГЛЯДЫ РУДАКИ О ВОСПИТАНИИ ЧЕЛОВЕКА АА Азимов - *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2023 515-523
8. SCIENCE, LITERATURE AND POETRY IN TRANSOXIANA AND KHORASAN IX-X CENTURIES.

9. AA Abdullayevich - MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE, 2023 247-260
10. Мирзакулов, Б. Т. (2015). Дипломатические и торговые связи Бухары с Россией XVI–XVIII вв. Молодой учёный, 20, 548.
11. Мирзакулов, Б. Т. (1994). Рабочая кооперация Узбекистана в 20-е-начале 30-х гг.
12. Atoyev, J. H., & Saloxov, A. Q. (2022). KONSTITUTSIYADA OILA HUQUQI. Academic research in educational sciences, 3(TSTU Conference 2), 637-640.
13. Salokhov, A. Q. (2023). METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF USING THE IDEAS OF BUKHARA NOVELTY IN FORMING TOLERANCE IN YOUNG PEOPLE. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(8), 171-178.
14. Салохов, А. К. К АНАЛИЗУ ИДЕЙ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ ТУРКЕСТАНСКОГО ДЖАДИДИЗМА В КОНТЕКСТЕ ЕЕ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ. ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ОЛИЙ ВА ЎРТА МАХСУС ТАЪЛИМ ВАЗИРЛИГИ МИРЗО УЛУҒБЕК НОМИДАГИ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН МИЛЛИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТИ ФУҚАРОЛИК ЖАМИЯТИ ШАКЛЛАНИШИНИ МОНИТОРИНГ, 464.
15. Салохов, А. Қ. БУХОРО МАЪРИФАТПАРВАРЧИЛИГИНИНГ ТАРИХИЙ-ФАЛСАФИЙ ТАҲЛИЛИ.
16. Murodov, S. A. (2022). Relationship between the universe and man in the works of Fariduddin Attor. In International conference: problems and scientific solutions (Vol. 1, No. 6, pp. 35-41).
17. Мурадов, С. А. Современные методы философии и их значение в развитии мышления человека. Актуальные исследования, 51.
18. Муродов, С. А. (2009). Ибн Сино, Аттор ва Навоий асарларида кушлар тимсоли. Имом ал-Бухорий сабоқлари», Маънавий-маърифий, илмий-адабий журнал. Тошкент, 273-276.
19. Мурадов, С. А. кизи Касимова, ФФ (2022, December). ФИЛОСОФИЯ ДИЗАЙНА: ОСОБЕННОСТИ И СУЩНОСТЬ. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 51-59).
20. Санжар, М. (2020). Взгляды Фаридуддина Аттара на бытие. Международный журнал прикладных исследований. ИДЖАР, 6(6), 34-36.
21. МУРАДОВ, С. А. СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ ФАРИДУДДИНА АТТОРА. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый, 51, 529-531.

22. Aslonovich, M. S., & Zaynura, M. (2023, June). NATIONAL DRESSES OF CENTRAL ASIA: AS A COMPONENT OF" CULTURE OF DESIGN". In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 170-177).
23. Aslonovich, M. S., & Zaynura, M. (2023, June). NATIONAL DRESSES OF CENTRAL ASIA: AS A COMPONENT OF" CULTURE OF DESIGN". In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 170-177).
24. Мурадов, С. А. (2023, June). ФАРИДУДДИН АТТОР-ВЕЛИКИЙ ШЕЙХ ВОСТОКА. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 149-160).
25. Muradov, S. A. (2023). THE MAIN IDEAS OF THE FOUNDER OF THE GERMAN SCHOOL OF PHILOSOPHY. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(7), 588-594.
26. Sanjar, M. One of the Factors of Purity of the Heart is Futuwwat. International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology, 98-101.
27. Sanjar, M. (2020). The views of Fariduddin Attar on being. International journal of applied research. IJAR, 6(6), 34-36.
28. Nurmatova N. U. THE WORK “MAQOMOTI YUSUF HAMADONIY” BY ABDULKHOLIK GHIJDUVONIY—A SAMPLE OF RESPECT TO THE MASTER” //Central Asian Problems of Modern Science and Education. – 2019. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 210-218.
29. Нурматова Н. У. ЮСУФ ҲАМАДОНИЙ ТОМОНИДАН ХОЖАГОН ТАЪЛИМОТИГА КИРИТИЛГАН БИРИНЧИ РАШҲА //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С. 565-576.
30. UMAROVNA, N. N. Four basis analysis of human perfection in the work of Yusuf Khamadani, Odobi tariqat. International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology, 7(4), 1-3.
31. Nurmatova N. U. Logical analysis of Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani’s work “Maqomoti Yusuf Hamadoni”/ISSN (Online): 2455-3662 EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)-Peer Reviewed Journal //Volume. – Т. 7. – С. 417-420.
32. Djuraev A. et al. Cotton increase the efficiency of cleaning as a result of improving the unit for cleaning small and large wastes //AIP Conference Proceedings. – AIP Publishing, 2023. – Т. 2789. – №. 1.
33. Нурматова, Нигора, and Нодиржон Сафоев. "ШКОЛА СУФИЗМА ЮСУФА ХАМАДОНИ В БУХАРЕ." INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE. Vol. 2. No. 15. 2023.

34. Нурматова Н. У. ЮСУФ ҲАМАДОНИЙ ТОМОНИДАН ХОЖАГОН ТАЪЛИМОТИГА КИРИТИЛГАН БИРИНЧИ РАШҲА //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С. 565-576.
35. Nurmatova, N. U. Logical analysis of Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani’s work “Maqomoti Yusuif Hamadoni”/ISSN (Online): 2455-3662 EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)-Peer Reviewed Journal. Volume, 7, 417-420.
36. Nurmatova N. U. THE WORK “MAQOMOTI YUSUF HAMADONIY” BY ABDULKHOLIK GHIJDUVONIY–A SAMPLE OF RESPECT TO THE MASTER” //Central Asian Problems of
37. Modern Science and Education. – 2019. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 210-218.
38. Нурматова Н. У. Юсуф Ҳамадоний ва хожагон-нақшбандия таълимотининг “назар бар қадам” рашҳаси //Zamonaviy oliy ta’lim: muammo va yechimlar. Xalqaro ilmiy konferensiya. Navoiy. – 2022. – С. 30-31.
39. Jahongir, S. (2020). Philosophical views of Umar life. Academicia. An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal.–India, 10(4), 360-364.
40. Shodiev, J. J. (2020). Interpretation of moral facts in the opinions of Umar Khayyam. International engineering journal for research & development.-India, 5(3), 143-148.
41. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. Interpretation of the image of may in the ruba of Umar Khayyam. Monografia pokonferencyjna science, research, development, 33, 2020-30.
42. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайём фалсафий қарашларида инсон тақдири ва эркин ирода масаласи. Наманган давлат университети Илмий ахборотномаси, 2, 197-204.
43. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайёмнинг асосий асарлари ва рубоийларининг тузилиши, мазмуни ва таҳлили. Илм Сарчашмалари.-Урганч, 10, 44-47.
44. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайём рубоийларининг талқин ва тавсифи. Наманган давлат университети Илмий ахборотномаси, 9, 206-210.
45. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайёмнинг ижтимоий-ахлоқий қарашлари. Фалсафа ва ҳуқуқ.–Тошкент, 3, 107-110.
46. Shodiev, J. (2021). The problem of knowledge in the philosophical views of Umar Khayyam. Imam al-Bukhari IBS Journal, 2.
47. Шодиев, Ж. (2022). Илк уйғониш даврида–комил инсонни шакллантириш ватарбиялашда тасаввуф таълимотининг ўрни. Scientific Bulletin of NamSU- Научный вестник НамГУ-NamDU ilmiy aхborotnomasi–2022-yil_4-сон, 229.
48. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. Мамлакатимизда инсон қадрини юксалтиришнинг ижтимоий-фалсафий масалалари. Қарду хабарлари. Илмий-назарий, услубий журнал. Махсус сон (Ижтимоий фанлар).

49. Shodiev, J. J. (2020). INTERPRETATION AND DESCRIPTION OF UMAR KHAYYAM RUBAYA. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University, 2(9), 206-211.
50. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2022). AGAINST IGNORANCE-FIGHTING WITH ENLIGHTENMENT THE MAIN CRITERIA IN IMPROVING HUMAN VALUE. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(10), 1160-1164.
51. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2022). ATTITUDE TO HUMAN DIGNITY IN THE PERIOD OF AMIR TEMUR AND TEMURIDS DYNASTY. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(5), 43-47.
52. Shodiyev, J. (2021). JAMIYATDAGI MEHNAT MUNOSABATLARI SHAROITIDA MA'NAVIY SALOHİYAT. Журнал истории и общества, (2)
53. SHODIEV, J. (2021). SOCIO-POLITICAL LIFE AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE IN THE PERIOD OF UMAR KHAYAM. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 1(1).
54. Shodiyev, J. (2021). O'ZBEKISTONDA IJTIMOİY-SIYOSIY KOMMUNIKATSIYA RIVOJLANISHIDA RAQAMLI TPANSFORMATSIYA SIYOSATI. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(2), 409-416.
55. Shodiyev, J. J. (2020). U THE QUESTION OF HUMAN DESTINY AND FREE IN THE PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF OMAR KHAYYAM. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 2(2), 197-202.
56. Shodiev Jahongir Jurakulovich. Interpretation of moral facts in the opinions of Umar Khayyam. International Engineering Journal For Research & Development 2020/4/16.
57. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2023). The role of the national idea in increase of human values. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(10), 1160-1164.
58. Shodiyev Jahongir Jo'raqulovich. Inson qadri va uning huquqlari eng oliy qadriyat: tarixiy-huquqiy meros. Ilm sarchashmalari/ Urganch – 3.2023. 19-21.
59. Shodiyev, J. J. (2023). THE ROLE OF SCIENTIFIC THINKING AND MENTAL DEVELOPMENT IN IMPROVING HUMAN DEVELOPMENT AND VALUE. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(9), 251-261.
60. Shodiyev, J. J. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE NATIONAL IDEA IN INCREASE OF HUMAN VALUES. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(7), 616-625.
61. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2023). PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF SAGES ON HUMAN VALUES AND GLORIFYING HIM. THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH, 2(16), 229-238.

62. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2023, June). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ИСТОРИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ В СОЗДАНИИ ФУНДАМЕНТА ТРЕТЬЕГО ВОЗРОЖДЕНИЯ И ЕГО ЗНАЧЕНИЕ В УКРЕПЛЕНИИ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКИХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 124-130).
63. JJ Shodiev. [A STEP TOWARDS HUMAN DIGNITY](#). GOLDEN BRAIN 1 (24), 59-67.
64. Музафаровна, А.М. (2022). СЕЛЬСКОХОЗЯЙСТВЕННАЯ РЕФОРМА И ВОЗНИКАЮЩИЕ КОНФЛИКТЫ. Международный междисциплинарный исследовательский журнал Galaxy , 10 (5), 623-626.
65. Гаффоров, А. Х., & Алимова, М. М. (2015). Интернационализация профессионального образования как требование времени. Молодой ученый, (2), 506-509.
66. Алимова, М. М. (2022, December). УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ВНУТРЕННЕЙ МОТИВАЦИЕЙ РАБОТНИКОВ НА БЕЗОПАСНЫЙ ТРУД И ВЫПОЛНЕНИЕ ТРЕБОВАНИЙ ОХРАНЫ ТРУДА. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS. (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 43-50).
67. Muzafarovna, A. M., & Tangrievich, M. B. (2021). FORCED COLLECTIVIZATION OF AGRICULTURE IN ZARAFSHAN OASIS (1928-1932). Thematics Journal of Education, 6(November).
68. Гаффоров, А. Х., & Алимова, М. М. (2016). Перспективы использования технологии сотрудничества в процессе подготовки педагога профессионального образования. Молодой ученый, (12), 839-841.
69. Гаффоров, А. Х., & Алимова, М. М. (2016). Психологические основы педагогического проектирования. Молодой ученый, (12), 837-839.
70. Гаффоров, А. Х., & Алимова, М. М. (2015). Социально-психологические факторы формирования модели педагога в современном образовательном процессе. Молодой ученый, (2), 504-506.
71. Алимова, М. М. (2023). «РАСКРЕПОЩЕНИЕ» ЖЕНЩИН В ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ (1920-1930 г. г). Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(8), 535-541.
72. Алимова, М. М., & Гариев, А. (2023). ПРОТИВОДЕЙСТВИЕ КОРРУПЦИИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH, 2(24), 261-270.
73. Бафоев Ф. М. Историческая память в мировой политике. Роль ООН и других международных организаций //Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук. – 2017. – №. 1-4. – С. 180-182.

74. Бафоев Ф. М. ПРИНЦИП НЕДЕЛИМОСТИ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ //Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук. – 2018. – №. 1-1. – С. 51-54.
75. БАФОЕВ Ф. М. О ВЗАИМОСВЯЗИ ГЛОБАЛЬНОЙ, РЕГИОНАЛЬНОЙ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПРОДОВОЛЬСТВЕННОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ //АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ Учредители: ООО" Агентство перспективных научных исследований". – №. 21. – С. 53-55.
76. БАФОЕВ Ф. М. К ВОПРОСУ КОРРЕКТИРОВКИ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ ПОНЯТИЯ «МИРОВАЯ ПОЛИТИКА» В КОНТЕКСТЕ СИНЕРГЕТИКИ //АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ. – С. 31.
77. БАФОЕВ Ф. М. К вопросу о динамике современных международных отношений //АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ Учредители: ООО" Агентство перспективных научных исследований", (20). – 2022. – С. 35-37.
78. Каримов, Б. (2011). Гармонизация взаимоотношений государства, общества и человека как основа справедливого общества. постановка вопроса. Fuqarolik jamiyati. Гражданское общество, 8(1), 71-73.
79. Каримов, БК (2021). Гармония разума и духа. Американский журнал социальных наук и инноваций в образовании , 3 (05), 230–234.
80. Каримов, Б. (2023). ПРОЦЕССЫ МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ В ДОКУМЕНТАХ ГЕНЕРАЛЬНОЙ АССАМБЛЕИ ООН (2017-2019). MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH, 2(24), 291-301.
81. Каримов, Б.К. (2023). СУЩНОСТЬ СОЗНАНИЯ И ЕГО ГЕНЕЗ. Инновационное развитие в образовательной деятельности , 2 (7), 532-539.
82. Aminovna, V. G. (2021). The role of social system and political ideas in achieving human prosperity. Thematics Journal of Education, 6(November).
83. Бердиева, Г. А. (2023). ПРАВОВАЯ И РЕЛИГИОЗНАЯ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТЬ В СРЕДНЕЙ АЗИИ В ПЕРИОД ПЕРВОГО РЕНЕССАНСА ВОСТОКА. МОДЕЛИ И МЕТОДЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ , 2 (24), 271-279.
84. Бердиева, Г. А. (2023). ПРИОРИТЕТЫ МОЛОДЕЖНОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(7), 524-531.
85. Бердиева, Г. А. (2023). ЁШЛАРНИ БАҒРИКЕНГЛИК РУҲИДА ТАРБИЯЛАШДА ИЖТИМОЙ ГУМАНИТАР ФАНЛАРНИНГ ТУТГАН ҲУРИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 5(NUU Conference 2), 232-240.
86. Аминовна, Б. Г. (2022). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ВНУТРЕННИХ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ПУТЕЙ СВЯЗИ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОАЗИАТСКИХ КОРОЛЕВСТВ В РАЗВИТИИ

- ТОРГОВЛИ. Web of Scientist: Международный научный исследовательский журнал, 3, 10-12.
87. Шукриллаев, Ю. А. (2006). Бухоро амирлигида кўшин ва ғарбий иш (1756-1920 йиллар). Тарих фанлари номзоди илмий дражасини олиш учун езилган диссертация.
88. Шукурллаев, Ю. (2022, December). СОЗДАНИЕ ВОЕННЫХ УСТАВНЫХ ГРУПП ЕВРОПЕЙСКОГО ТИПА В БУХАРСКОМ ЭМИРАТЕ. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE" THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS" (Vol. 1, No. 4, pp. 42-51).
89. Шукруллаев, Ю. А. Армия Бухарского эмирата и военное дело (1756-1920 гг.). Автореферат кандидатской диссертации по истории.-Ташкент, 2006.-26 с.; К вопросу о дипломатических сношениях между Россией и Бухарой через Оренбург в конце XVIII-начале XIX веков. Общественные науки в Узбекистане.-1962, 7, 55-59.
90. Shukrullayev, Y. A. The Army of Bukhara Emirate and Military Affairs (1756-1920). Synopsis of candidate dissertation in history.-Tashkent, 2006.-26 pp.; On the Issue of Diplomatic Relations between Russia and Bukhara through Orenburg at the End of the XVIII-th-the Beginning of the XIX-th Centuries. Social Sciences in Uzbekistan.-1962, 7, 55-59.
91. Shukrullayev, Y. A., & Bahritdinovna, S. R. (2023). GERMANIYA FEDERATIV RESPUBLIKASI IQTISODIYOTINI TIKLASH HARAKATI.“IQTISODIY MO ‘JIZA”. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(7), 577-587.
92. Shukrullayev, Y. A. (2022). FRANSIYA–O ‘ZBEKISTON ALOQALARINING TARIXIY ILDIZLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 1(3), 110-113.
93. Шукурллаев, Ю. (2023). ВОЕННЫЕ РЕФОРМЫ В БУХАРСКОМ ЭМИРАТЕ ПОД ПРОТЕКТОРАТОМ. THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH, 2(16), 249-260.
94. Шукурллаев, Ю. А. (2023). БУХОРО АМИРЛИГИДА КЎШИН ТАРКИБИГА ҚАБУЛ ҚИЛИШ ҚОИДАЛАРИ, АСКАРЛАРНИНГ ҚЎШИН ТАРКИБИДАН ҚОЧИШИ (ДЕЗЕРТИРСВО), САБАБИ ВА ОҚИБАТЛАРИ. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(8), 513-524.
95. Shukurillayev, Y. (2023). Sherbachus and Afghan Groups in the Emirate of Bukhara. Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal, 2(1), 34-36.
96. Sultanova, L. (2021). The historical roots of spiritual education of youth. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(3), 461-463.
97. Mavlonova, I., Akhmetjanov, M., Vokhidova, M., Fayziev, S., & Shokirova, S. (2022, December). Experimental studies of the dynamics of the proposed design of the

presser foot with an additional conical spring. In Journal of Physics: Conference Series (Vol. 2373, No. 2, p. 022047). IOP Publishing.

98. Vohidova, M. (2023). SOCIAL AND ETHICAL ASPECTS OF THE EXISTENCE OF TOLERANCE IN YOUNG PEOPLE. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(6), 559-566.

99. Вахидова, М. Т., & Мирзаев, У. Т. (2022, December). ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ КУЛЬТУРЫ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ В УСЛОВИЯХ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE " THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS" (Vol. 1, No. 4, pp. 52-62).

100. Вахидова, М. Т. (2022). ДУХОВНО-НРАВСТВЕННОЕ ВОСПИТАНИЕ МОЛОДЕЖИ УЗБЕКИСТАН В КОНТЕКСТЕ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE, 1(7), 82-90.

101. Султонова, Л. С. (2023). ИЖТИМОЙ-ГУМАНИТАР ФАНЛАРНИ ЎҚИТИШДА ПЕДАГОГИК ИННОВАЦИЯ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН ФАОЛИЯТНИНГ УЗВИЙЛИГИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 5(NUU Conference 2), 633-639.

102. Sultonova, L. (2023). Upbringing Mature Person. Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture, 4(3), 71-73.

103. Султанова, Л. С. (2023). ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТЬ В ВОСПИТАНИИ ПОДРОСТОЯЩЕГО ПОКОЛЕНИЯ. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(7), 557-564.

104. Султонова, Л. С. (2022). МЕСТО ИНЖЕНЕРНОЙ ПЕДАГОГИКИ В ПОДГОТОВКЕ БУДУЩИХ ИНЖЕНЕРОВ. YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS, 1(6), 29-34.